

PLAIN WEAVE REINFORCEMENT IN C/C COMPOSITES VISUALISED IN 3D FOR ELASTIC PARAMETRES

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Keywords: *Layered structures, elastic properties, finite element analysis (FEA), prepreg*

1 Introduction

The article deals with multi-scale modelling in three-dimensional model. Main focus was concerned to the meso-level which is in our case the basic unit cell of plain weave reinforcement consists from cross linked infinite fibre bundles.

Construction of models allows classical weave of woven reinforcement but also slides places during lamination process and curing. Anyway some idealization was also necessary in study of its symmetry.

Composites with textile reinforcement have got good resistance against to progression of cracks and give good tensile properties in warp and weft directions. However the structure modelling of composites is than a complex problem. Here is irregularly crimped textile reinforcement with various inherent defects (pores, bubbles and cracks) which has risen during pyrolysis process of polymer precursor in carbon matrix. Different shrinkage during cooling plays its role too [1, 2].

Lamination gives to the structure imperfection in faze of woven reinforcement thus defects can rise in areas full of matrix whereas same direction bundles lie on each other. It is difficult to include all aspects of this complex structure to one model. The idealisation is based on geometric models as the bricks or sinusoidal curve of woven reinforcement [3, 4].

Composites with weave reinforcement structure were studied by image analysis at the Technical University of Liberec.

1.1 Material

Material was set on carbon/carbon composite which was already tested with classical tests so results should be proved and corrected.

Fig. 1. Image of woven reinforcement composite cross-section – example 1 view of interlace

Fig. 2. Image of woven reinforcement composite cross-section – example 2 view of vacuole

Presented results are based on carbon material input values. The real composite, our tested material for real image structure observation, was made from carbon materials.

Carbon and carbon fibres have got unique properties. Carbon fibres embody special alternatives in

symmetry. If we compare carbon in various stages with other materials we can find high correlation of Young's modulus on density. Different materials were metal, wood, elements, glass, rubber, porcelain etc.

Density and Young's modulus correlation for various basic materials is minimal. However line for glassy carbon, graphite and diamond correlate very high, see Fig. 3.

Mass density and Young's modulus for materials were gathered mainly from internet research on Web of Knowledge, Google, Science Direct from journal articles and product material sheets.

Fig. 3. Correlation density-Young's modulus for different common materials and carbons

When we compare basic carbons with carbon fibres correlation we find even higher dependency between mass density and Young's modulus. Fig. 4. gives us this relation clear. Fibres not only from carbon are highly oriented along the structure because of the process spinning from spinneret.

Fibre is extruded through the thin spinneret and orientation along the fibre axis organizes bonds inside the fibre in this preferable direction. We use it as a benefit for composite construction. Bundles multiply reinforcing effect and weaving spread this effect to the symmetry in two directions across.

Fig. 4. Correlation density-Young's modulus for carbons and carbon fibres

We based our modelling on the real composite prepared by prepreg technology. The tested composite was layered laminate from carbon fibre in plain weave surrounded with carbon matrix.

Fibres were graphitized so the structure is highly oriented along fibre axis with transversal isotropy symmetry presumption.

Matrix was prepared from phenolic resin with high-temperature treatment to the carbonized temperature so the presumption is that matrix has got glassy carbon structure with isotropic orientation.

Bundle is made from 6000 parallel infinite high strength carbon fibres. Important input properties are in Table 1.

Component	Density [kg.m ⁻³]	Young's modulus [MPa]	Poisson's ratio [-]
Fibres	1810	294 000	0,24
Matrix	1400	89	0,30
Voids - air	1,3	0,0	0,0

Table 1 Values of important input mechanical properties

The computation without a plastic deformation by scanning of stress and strain concentrations and it is also possible to evaluate elastic constants.

An alternative model for determining properties of future composite construction is a calculation which we do with commercial software. The structure modelling in multi-scale supports calculation in finite element method effectively.

2 Models and Computation

2.1 Multi-scale modelling

The multi-scale modelling allows decomposition of complex heterogeneous structure to the partial levels from the simplest composition to the composition of whole sample body. The main sources for the theory equations and relations were work of Berthelot [5], Bogdanovich [4], Lomov [3] and Miravete [6].

Bogdanovich 3D mosaic model should describe basic idea of composition when computation from lower level are used in higher level as an local input of the complex higher structure [4].

Original research of Bogdanovich ([4] Bogdanovich A.E.: Three-dimensional variation theory of laminated composite plates and its implementation with Bernstein basis function. *Comput. Methods Appl. Engrg.* 185 279-304, Elsevier, 2000.) was used as a key theory source also in the previous research of author of this paper in 2D modelling presented by Těšínová-Vozková, Salačová in "Elastic Properties of Woven Composite" published at the Comsol Users Conference 2006 Prague. In this earlier work the model described on page 1 belongs to the Prof. Bogdanovich and the reference was missed in the text by mistake.

Fig. 5. Brick nomenclature in 3D mosaic model by Bogdanovich [4]

2.2 Model Description

On Fig. 6. is parting to the scales. A simulation in our case presents the two-dimensional model and three-dimensional model of lengthwise and crosswise fibre bundles surrounded with matrix. Defects are mentioned here, too. It is necessary to include defects in the bundles, between laminas and voids raised during pyrolysis and layering. Whole structure is a combination of geometry formations. Modelling is described in more detail in literature [7, 8].

Fig. 6. Multi-scale models in 2D: fibre + matrix, bundle + defects, periodic unit cells, lamina [7]

Fig. 7. Multi-scale models in 3D: fibre + matrix, bundle + defects, periodic unit cells, lamina [8]

Composite is composed from bundles cross-linked in the woven structure and based lamina. Whole composite is that constructed simply by two types of lamina to the plain structure. We study preferably composites in plain because of the simplicity of formulation of results and because we are focused to the structure. Pure mechanical description can count with selection of "black box" and have good results for composite, but it is mainly based on experiment. We work with real composites to obtain inside structure of the reinforcement and try to idealize as less as possible.

Scale and type of the tested sample	length [m]	high [m]
Crosswise bundle	$2,2 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$1,8 \cdot 10^{-5}$
Lengthwise bundle	$2,2 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$1,8 \cdot 10^{-5}$
Crosswise bundle with defects	$1,8 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$1,8 \cdot 10^{-4}$
Lengthwise bundle section with defects	$1,8 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$1,8 \cdot 10^{-4}$
Structure unit cell 1	$4,5 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$0,3 \cdot 10^{-3}$
Structure unit cell 2	$4,5 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$0,5 \cdot 10^{-3}$
Lamina 1	0,0315	$0,3 \cdot 10^{-3}$
Lamina 2	0,0315	$0,5 \cdot 10^{-3}$
Whole composite structure	0,0315	$1,5 \cdot 10^{-3}$

Table 2 Multi-scale model dimensions

In our multi-scale model it is counted with whole model in stages from fibres to bundles but in previous research we used third type of basic unit cell which we now neglected because our recommended composites contain (with pressure 0.5 MPa for 6 layers) just two basic types of basic unit cell: without defects in proper lay-out and in translation where defects are inside the structure. Optimal number of defects is occurred in type of composites.

2.3 Software Used For Computation

In the experiment here is a description of the results obtained from the simulation in Comsol Multiphysics™. which is used for calculation with proper determination of the material properties, boundary states and net adjusting.

2.4 Model Presumptions

Sample was clamped on one side and loaded in the axis x thus model was tested for simple stress strain characteristic in elastic area of loading to find elastic modulus.

2.5 Stress Concentrations in Models

The longitudinal stress of fibre-matrix focus to bundle is concentrated in the fibres and stressed mostly where fibres are close to each other and matrix cannot spread loading so effectively. Mean stress is in the middle of the fibres. The crosswise bundle with defects has got the highest longitudinal stress in the carbon part near defects horizontal curvature. A minimum is everywhere else.

The concentration of the stress and of the strain is highly affected by the occurrence of the defects in the carbon part. The carbon part carries stress and the pores localize strain.

Unit cell level is described with the following figures. Structure unit cell 1 concentrates stress in whole bundle. This bundle is lengthwise to the loading. Maximum stress is located in the parts which hold the loading longitudinal. However stress is not the same in all area of the bundle.

It is caused by the higher stress in the thinner sample place of further area. It caused that stress from tension is than not located in the centre of the bundle length but close the contact point. When we focus to the axis x we can observe maximal loading in the curvature and changing of the curvature where bundle goes from one binding point to the next and is than surrounded only with the matrix.

Holding of the load is mostly on the fibres here and matrix only spread tension to the neighbouring fibres and bundles. For better predicative of relation matrix was not visualised but loading was not on maximum at that parts.

Fig. 8. Unit cell 1 stress computation in visualisation of cross-section in axis z

Fig. 9. Unit cell 1 stress computation in visualisation of cross-section in axis x

Anyway maximal loaded area was observed in the middle of the structure in the bundle where curvature if the bundle changed from one contact point to the next. Next the higher stress is located in the curvature places where contact surfaces with bundles with cross direction on that position.

Defects embodies tendency to the deformation and strain is located in them. Matrix surrounded defects is than under the tension and spread loading to the neighbouring part of the bundle so it is the more reason why lengthwise bundles are at maximum loading when they are surrounded by matrix in this scale of model.

The unit cell 1 has got more balanced loading for the stress properties than unit cell 2. The longitudinal stress is high here but not really critical for both, we are still in the elastic relations without deformation so we detected only tension no plastic deformation. Curvature and matrix apply a load to the lengthwise bundles the most. Also cross bundles affects not allowance against flotation.

Fig. 10. Unit cell 2 stress computation in visualisation of cross-section in axis x

Fig. 12. Unit cell 2 stress computation in visualisation of cross-section in axis z

Laminas have got the highest stress and strain in the whole area. The lamina is combined from bricks with the same parameters so these results are expected. The whole composite combined from laminas has got longitudinal stress close to the clamped end of the sample similarly like single lamina. The higher impact goes farther for lamina which it has got higher longitudinal stress from the previous single testing. But impact is the same no matter which lamina it is.

3 Results and discussion

Simulations with the finite element method are fast and precise same as a resonant oscillation experiment. Both methods were compared.

Relations in following graphs were interpolated with equation included calculation of axis in plane [9].

Loading in on axis direction has to be transferred to the symmetry axis in defined angle δ [-]. Loading is then transferred to the main directions. Longitudinal modulus could be defined with inclusion constants from compliance tensor [9]

$$\frac{1}{E_x} = \frac{1}{E_L} \cos^4 \delta + \frac{1}{E_T} \sin^4 \delta + \left(\frac{1}{G_{LT}} - \frac{2\mu_{LT}}{E_L} \right) \cos^2 \delta \sin^2 \delta \quad (1)$$

where E_x is longitudinal modulus in any angle [Pa], E_L is Young's modulus [Pa], E_T is transversal modulus [Pa], G_{LT} is shear modulus [Pa], μ_{LT} is Poisson's ratio [-], angle δ is varied in whole 360° in plane of reinforcement through warp and weft twice [9].

$$G_{xy}(\delta) = \left[2 \left(\frac{4(1+\mu)}{E} - \frac{1}{G} \right) \sin^2 \delta \cos^2 \delta + \frac{1}{G} (\sin^4 \delta + \cos^4 \delta) \right]^{-1} \quad (2)$$

where E , G and μ are Young's modulus, shear modulus and Poisson number for xy axis in-plane where axis X_1 has go direction of warp [9].

Experiment was tested at Department of Structure and Mechanics of Rocks of Science Academy of the Czech Republic and was used as a special comparing property for the multi-scale simulation [9].

Fig. 13. Young's modulus for carbonised composite samples from eigen frequency experiment

Fig. 14. Young's modulus for graphitised composite samples from eigen frequency experiment

The experiment was compared with a simulation and it is visualized in diagrams for the in-plane treatment in the plain weave reinforcement.

Model was set as clamped on left side in the axis x and loaded for tensile test along axis x . Only axis x was in deformation to elongation, the other sides should be on shrinkage because no other restrictions for roll of fix on the sided of model to test as close to real experiment as possible.

Scale and type of the tested sample		Longitudinal modulus for warp [MPa]
		Model axis x
2D	Unit cell 1	54813 <56332;53294>
	Unit cell 2	62375 <64104;60646>
3D	Unit cell 1	38768 <39842;37693>
	Unit cell 2	49751 <51130;48372>
Composite from experiment		103000 <105854;100145>
Whole composite structure from simulation 2D		85968 <88350;83585>
Whole composite structure from simulation 3D		102283 <105118;99447>

Table 3 Values of mechanical properties – Longitudinal modulus for warp [MPa]

Scale and type of the tested sample		Transversal modulus [MPa]
		Model axis y
2D	Unit cell 1	408 <419;397>
	Unit cell 2	717 <736;697>
3D	Unit cell 1	3056 <3140;2971>
	Unit cell 2	3782 <3886;3677>
Composite from experiment		-
Whole composite structure from simulation 2D		572 <587;556>
Whole composite structure from simulation 3D		3444 <3539;3348>

Table 4 Values of mechanical properties – Transversal modulus in-plane of textile [MPa]

Scale and type of the tested sample		Longitudinal modulus for weft [MPa]
		Model axis z
2D	Unit cell 1	54813 <56332;53293>
	Unit cell 2	62375 <64103;60646>
3D	Unit cell 1	43837 <45052;42621>
	Unit cell 2	47816 <49141;46490>
Composite from experiment		108000 <110993;105006>
Whole composite structure from simulation 2D		85968 <88350;83585>
Whole composite structure from simulation 3D		105992 <108929;103054>

Table 5 Values of mechanical properties - Longitudinal modulus for weft [MPa]

Fig. 15. Unit cell longitudinal modulus computed from various methods and models in comparison

Unit cell level in 2D model occurs a bit higher values of the longitudinal modulus but it is caused mainly by the model.

Loading should be spread only to the two dimensions thus one lengthwise bundle or two in the only one direction hold the loading as predicted.

In the 3D model loading is spread to the sample and curvature or more matrix amount in the sample body. The presence of the weak point is more

probable. Though this, let say, disadvantage is getting better results in the higher levels.

In lamina and in the composite body is 3D the reason why whole composite longitudinal modulus is a bit better to 2D type of model.

In this type of model where we count it as a one component loading is better to be transferred to the directions and results are getting higher. Anyway this difference is not critical and both results are comparable and with good agreement with the experiment.

Fig. 16. Whole composite longitudinal modulus computed from various methods, models and experiment in comparison

The conclusion from the previous pages follows as estimation between the experiment and the simulation of elastic properties of the carbon/carbon composite with the plain weave reinforcement. We used models in two types 2D and 3D.

The simulation and experiment correlate well for longitudinal modulus of the whole composite in all directions in the in-plane of the reinforcement, for 3D model even better than 2D. The theory agrees well for it where warp and weft reinforce composite greatly. The simulation was adapted quite well for the real composite.

Combination of the multi-scale and the finite element simulation provide relevant data of the elastic modules which is confirmed by the used experiment. More directions are offered to the evaluation and not only isotropic structure is possible to be used.

3 Conclusion

Simulation helps to evaluate properties in longitudinal and also in the transversal directions for material with an orthotropic properties.

The simulation with the multi-scale modelling is necessary to evaluate precise input values for the lowest scale.

Simulation helps to evaluate properties in longitudinal and also in the transversal directions for material with an orthotropic properties. More directions are offered to the evaluation and not only isotropic structure is possible to be used. It is an advantage of the experiment.

Some more advanced sample preparing should be done in the future for making thin plates in different directions of the composite especially for the direction transversely to the reinforcement.

The most influencing factor for the elastic properties is an amount of the lengthwise bundles, the position of the crosswise bundles with the matrix properties and of the defects. Defects work upon all others modulus too.

The simulation with the multi-scale modelling is necessary to evaluate precise input values for the lowest scale. Here it is not problem with the fibre testing. Many methods are used and suitable. The matrix properties are more complicated to obtain and it is necessary to be patient and precise in determination.

Previous non-destructive testing is possible to use for any material with the similar structure and the same prepreg technology. If geometry models on the Periodic unit cell scale are adapted, different technology should be evaluated with the same procedure too.

Both methods presented here, the experiment and the finite element simulation, are good instrument together for the testing of the elastic properties and preparing of the new composites with varied structure or material properties.

It is also useful to compute from whole structure with defined end properties and find out components with ability to construct.

Acknowledgements

The work was financially supported by the grant GA106/09/P648 of the Czech Science Foundation.

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